

Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security

Horizon Europe projects ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, & LAMASUS release joint prespective paper offering new insights for the future of EU agri-food policy

July 24, 2025

The three Horizon Europe research projects — **LAMASUS**, **BrightSpace**, and **ACT4CAP27** — launched a joint perspective paper entitled:

“Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security – An economic modellers’ perspective.”

This joint publication provides a timely contribution to the ongoing debate on the future of agriculture and food systems in Europe. It emphasises that **a sustainable agricultural sector is not only essential for achieving environmental goals but is also central to ensuring economic resilience, food security, and broader societal well-being across the EU.**

Drawing on the combined expertise of economic modellers and policy analysts from across Europe, the paper sets out how scientific insights can support more coherent, evidence-based agricultural policymaking in the years ahead — particularly in the context of the **post-2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** and the European Commission’s **Vision for Agriculture and Food**.

Five Priority Action Areas

The authors highlight **five Priority Action Areas (PAAs)** where action is urgently needed to support a thriving and sustainable EU agricultural sector:

PAA1. Fostering income and resilience through result-based policies that integrate economic and environmental performance.

PAA2. Integrated nutrient management to enhance strategic autonomy.

PAA3. Enhancing the agrifood sector competitiveness and food security through level-playing field trade agreements.

PAA4. Strengthening innovation leadership in the new bioeconomy.

PAA5. Democratizing digitalization to ensure agricultural sector attractiveness and technological innovation.

These priority areas reflect both short-term policy needs and longer-term structural challenges. They also offer opportunities for the EU to strengthen its position as a global leader in sustainable agriculture.

“Realizing the full contribution of the agricultural sector to economic prosperity, food security and environmental sustainability requires both innovations and policies that foster synergies between the public and private sectors and different policy objectives.”

Dr. Petr Havlík, Deputy Director, Energy, Climate, and Environment Programme, IIASA
Scientific coordinator of LAMASUS and lead co-author of the perspective paper

Integrated Modelling for Better Policy

The paper demonstrates how advanced policy modelling tools — such as **CAPRI**, **GLOBIOM**, and **MAGNET** — can be used to evaluate trade-offs, anticipate systemic risks, and explore future scenarios. By combining economic, environmental, and social indicators, these models help decision-makers assess the impact of different policy options across the EU and beyond.

“ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and LAMASUS are uniquely positioned to contribute to the European Commission’s Vision for Agriculture and Food by improving the tools and data that underpin EU policy. Our joint work helps close knowledge gaps and supports more forward-looking, coherent decision-making.”

Prof. Hans van Meijl, Senior Researcher, Wageningen Social and Economic Research
Scientific coordinator of BrightSpace and ACT4CAP27, co-author of the perspective paper

The joint perspective paper is part of a broader commitment by the three Horizon Europe projects to support the European Commission’s strategic agenda through robust scientific collaboration. It builds on the projects’ ongoing engagement with policy stakeholders, including recent workshops, dialogues, and presentations at DG AGRI.

Access the perspective paper

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131>

Contact

For media inquiries and further details, please reach out to our Joint Paper Communications Coordination Team:

Petr HAVLÍK, email: havlikpt@iiasa.ac.at

Further information

ACT4CAP27: Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

<https://act4cap27.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

BrightSpace: Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space |

<https://brightspace-project.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060075>

LAMASUS: LAnd use and MAnagement modelling for SUStainable governance |

<https://www.lamasus.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060423>

